

Bidirectional approach to symmetrical spiro-1,3-biketone via Grignard reaction and two fold ring-closing metathesis as key steps

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Abstract : We have developed a useful method for the construction of symmetrical spiro-1,3-biketone starting with a commercially available diethylmalonate by using double Grignard addition and two fold ring-closing metathesis as key steps. During the Grignard reaction, we observed 1,4-addition without involvement of copper catalyst.

Keywords : Grignard reaction, ring-closing metathesis, spirocyclics, 1,4-addition reaction.

Introduction

Since last two decades, olefin metathesis¹ has become a useful tool in the organic synthesis for the construction of C-C bonds. To this end, introduction of well-defined ruthenium complexes² (**1-4**) shown in Fig. 1 played a critical role. Design and synthesis of spirocyclics is considered as a challenging task due to the creation of a quaternary center. Moreover, the construction of spirocyclic systems³ is of considerable importance because the spiro linkage is a key structural element present in various biologically active molecules as well as theo-

retically interesting targets⁴. Ring-closing metathesis (RCM) is a useful protocol to generate various spirocyclics involving carbocyclic as well as heterocyclic rings^{5,6}.

Although, numerous methods are available in the literature for the synthesis of spirocyclics, still there is a continuous need for the development of new strategies to expand the chemical space of spirocyclics to a higher level. As a part of our program aimed to develop new strategies to spirocyclics, we conceived a simple strategy involving double Grignard addition and two fold RCM as key steps to generate spirocyclic systems **8a-c** (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Metathesis catalysts.

Fig. 2. Our strategy toward the synthesis of symmetrical spiro-1,3-biketones.

Results and discussion

Our strategy toward the synthesis of symmetrical spiro-1,3-biketones **8a-c** started with the dialkenylation of commercially available starting material diethylmalonate **5** by using aq. NaOH (12.5 M) in the presence of phase-transfer catalyst benzyltriethylammonium chloride (BTEAC) to deliver the known compounds **6a** (95%), **6b** (39%), **6c** (65%) respectively (Scheme 1)⁷⁻⁹. When these dialkenylated compounds **6a-c** were treated with vinylmagnesium bromide, we observed 1,4-addition of vinyl group to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds **12a-c** formed by the replacement of ethoxy group of compounds **6a-c** with vinyl group to afford the tetraenes **7a** (47%), **7b** (43%), **7c** (40%) respectively along with the triene **7d** (18%) (Scheme 1). The structure of these compounds **7a-c** and **7d** have been confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data and further supported by HRMS data. Although, in literature it is reported that during vinyl Grignard reaction without any additive to conjugated enone 1,2-addition¹⁰ is more favorable, but in our case, we observed 1,4-addition without any copper catalyst.

Having the tetraenes **7a-c** in hand, they were treated with (G-I) catalyst in dry CH₂Cl₂. The RCM reaction of **7a** afforded the compounds **8a** (71%) and **9** (24%) (Scheme 1). During the RCM sequence, we did not observe the formation of the compound **10**. On the other hand, the compounds **7b** and **7c** were unable to deliver the desired products **8b** and **8c** under similar reaction conditions.

Later, we have also tried various different reaction conditions with different metathesis catalysts (e.g. G-I, G-II, GH-II) by varying the mol% of catalysts and changing the solvents, but in all cases we obtained the unidentified complex reaction mixture. Having the compound **8a** in hand, it was hydrogenated by using the Pd/C in EtOAc under hydrogen atmosphere (1 atm) to deliver the symmetrical spiro-1,3-biketone **11** in 96% yield (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Commercially available reagents were used without purification and the reactions involving air sensitive reagents or catalysts were performed in degassed solvents. Moisture sensitive materials were transferred by using standard syringe-septum techniques and the reactions were maintained under nitrogen atmosphere. Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on (7.5 × 2.5 cm) glass plates coated with Acme's silica gel GF-254 (containing 13% calcium sulfate as a binder) by using appropriate mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether for development. Column chromatography was performed by using Acme's silica gel (100–200 mesh) with an appropriate mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether. The coupling constants (*J*) are given in hertz (Hz) and chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million (ppm). The abbreviations, s, d, t, q, m, dd and td, refer to singlet, doublet, triplet, quartet, multiplet, doublet of doublet, and triplet of doublet respectively. Grubbs' catalysts were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Infrared (IR)

Scheme 1. Synthesis of spiro-1,3-biketone via Grignard reaction and RCM.

spectra were recorded on Nicolet Impact-400 FT IR spectrometer in KBr/(neat). Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR, 400 MHz and 500 MHz) spectra and carbon nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR, 100 MHz and 125 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer. The high-resolution mass measurements were carried out by using electrospray ionization (ESI), (Q-ToF) spectrometer. Melting points were recorded on a Büchi B-545 melting point apparatus.

General procedure for the preparation of compounds 6a-c : To an aq. NaOH (12.5 N) solution, BTEAC (1 equiv) and compound **5** at 0 °C were added, the reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min at rt. Later, alkenyl bromides (2.5 equiv) were added and the stirring was continued at rt. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude products were purified by silica gel column chromatography (appropriate mixture of EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the compounds **6a-c** as thick colourless liquids. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra matched with the literature reported spectral data⁷⁻⁹.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds 7a-c : To a solution of compounds **6a-c** in dry THF (10–20 mL), was added vinyl magnesium bromide (1 M in THF, 6 equiv) at 0 °C and stirred the reaction mixture at rt. for 13–18 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL) and the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude products were purified by silica gel column chromatography (2–3% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the thick colorless liquids **7a-c**.

Synthesis of compound 7a : To a solution of compound **6a** (400 mg, 1.66 mmol) in dry THF (20 mL), was added vinyl magnesium bromide (1 M in THF, 6 equiv) at 0 °C and stirred the reaction mixture at rt. for 16 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL) and the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (2% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the thick colorless liquid **7a** (205 mg, 47%) along

with the compound **7d** (82 mg, 18%).

Compound 7a : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.27–2.32 (4H, m), 2.42–2.46 (4H, m), 2.68 (4H, d, J 7.32 Hz), 4.96–5.13 (8H, m), 5.45–5.55 (2H, m), 5.69–5.80 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 27.61, 35.05, 39.03, 69.77, 115.85, 119.46, 132.13, 136.85, 206.96; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1635, 2928, 2976 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{NaO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 283.1669, Found : 283.1674.

Compound 7d : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.22 Hz), 2.31–2.34 (2H, m), 2.48–2.52 (2H, m), 2.60–2.64 (4H, m), 4.19 (2H, q, J_1 7.22 Hz, J_2 14.24 Hz), 4.95–5.12 (6H, m), 5.53–5.58 (2H, m), 5.59–5.78 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (125.8 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 14.30, 27.91, 36.15, 38.71, 61.56, 63.13, 115.53, 119.36, 132.39, 137.20, 171.71, 205.57; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1641, 1713, 1740, 2982 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{NaO}_3$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 273.1461, Found : 273.1461.

Synthesis of compound 7b : To a solution of compound **6b** (150 mg, 0.56 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL), was added vinyl magnesium bromide (1 M in THF, 6 equiv) at 0 °C and stirred the reaction mixture at rt. for 13 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL) and the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (3% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the thick colourless liquid **7b** (69 mg, 43%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.69–1.80 (4H, m), 1.99–2.04 (4H, m), 2.27–2.34 (4H, s), 2.41–2.52 (4H, m), 4.96–5.05 (8H, m), 5.69–5.81 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 27.79, 28.14, 29.49, 38.63, 70.04, 115.42, 115.94, 136.93, 137.58, 207.97; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1261, 1439, 1712, 2915, 3061 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{NaO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 311.1987, Found : 311.1977.

Synthesis of compound 7c : To a solution of compound **6c** (200 mg, 0.67 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL), was added vinyl magnesium bromide (1 M in THF, 6 equiv) at 0 °C and stirred the reaction mixture at rt. for 18 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated aq. NH_4Cl solu-

tion (5 mL) and the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (2% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the thick colourless liquid **7c** (85 mg, 40%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.70–1.81 (5H, m), 1.99–2.03 (5H, m), 2.26–2.32 (5H, s), 2.40–2.44 (5H, m), 4.95–5.06 (8H, m), 5.69–5.81 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 27.79, 28.13, 29.43, 31.68, 38.62, 70.00, 115.43, 115.96, 136.93, 137.58, 208.01; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1265, 1441, 1708, 2890, 3048 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{32}\text{NaO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 339.2290, Found : 339.2294.

Preparation of compound 8a : Grubb's first generation catalyst (41 mg, 10 mol%) was added to a degassed solution of tetraene **7a** (130 mg, 0.5 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (20 mL) under nitrogen atmosphere and the reaction mixture was stirred at rt. for 18 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (3% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to deliver the thick colourless liquid **8a** (73 mg, 71%) along with the compound **9** (28 mg, 24%). The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral data of compound **8a** was matched with the literature reported spectral data¹¹.

Compound 9 : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 2.23–2.31 (4H, m), 2.33–2.43 (4H, m), 2.83 (4H, s), 4.89–5.52 (4H, m), 5.65 (2H, s), 5.67–5.73 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 28.21, 37.74, 38.35, 73.21, 115.89, 128.17, 136.91, 206.46; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1623, 1708, 2854, 2932 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{NaO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 255.1356, Found : 255.1358.

Synthesis of compound 11 : The solution of compound **10** (53 mg, 0.26 mmol) and Pd/C (12 mg, 20 mol%) in dry ethyl acetate (10 mL) was stirred under hydrogen atmosphere (1 atm) at rt. for 24 h. At the conclusion of reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was filtered through the sintered funnel and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (5% EtOAc-petroleum ether) to afford the compound **11** (52 mg, 96%) as a white solid, m.p. 74–76 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 1.20–1.29 (2H, m), 1.39–1.85 (12H, m),

2.30–2.44 (4H, m), 2.64–2.70 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 24.37, 26.83, 30.48, 31.55, 41.09, 71.31, 211.10; IR (neat) : ν_{max} 1686, 2855, 2936 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI, Q-ToF) m/z : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{NaO}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 231.1356, Found : 231.1351.

Conclusion

We have established an efficient and useful method for the synthesis of symmetrical spiro-1,3-bis(ketone) **11** by the application of double Grignard addition and two fold RCM sequence as key steps. We have also first time shown 1,4-addition of vinyl group to geminally substituted malonic ester derivatives in the absence of copper catalyst.

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